

Postoperative Stridor and Respiratory Failure Following Hypospadias Repair in a Toddler with Prior Croup: A Case Report

Authors:

Thoayba Gaafer Mahgoub Elhassan¹, Hussein Mahmoud², Hind Ismail Khaleel³

Affiliations:

¹Specialist A, Department of Anesthesiology, Sharjah.

²Anesthesiologist, Department of Anesthesiology, Sharjah.

³Head of Department, Department of Anesthesiology, Sharjah.

Corresponding Author

Thoayba Gaafer Mahgoub Elhassan, Specialist A, Department of Anesthesiology, Sharjah.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18812617>

Received: 01-January-2025, Revised: 18-January-2026, Accepted: 26-February-2026, Online First: 01-March-2026

ABSTRACT:

Postoperative stridor is an uncommon but potentially life-threatening complication in pediatric anesthesia. We report a 22-month-old boy undergoing elective hypospadias repair who developed severe postoperative stridor and respiratory failure despite an uneventful anesthetic course. Initial therapy with systemic corticosteroids and nebulized epinephrine provided temporary improvement, but progressive airway obstruction necessitated high-flow nasal cannula, followed by endotracheal intubation and mechanical ventilation. Subglottic edema and pulmonary opacities consistent with atelectasis or aspiration contributed to respiratory distress. The patient recovered after 72 hours of ventilatory support. This case highlights the importance of meticulous preoperative airway evaluation, early recognition of postoperative airway compromise, and a low threshold for escalation in children with prior upper airway disease.

Keywords: *Postoperative stridor, Pediatric anesthesia, Subglottic edema, Upper airway obstruction, Hypospadias repair, Respiratory failure.*

INTRODUCTION:

Postoperative stridor in pediatric patients is an infrequent yet high-risk airway complication. Even minor mucosal edema can cause significant airway narrowing in infants and toddlers due to their naturally small airway diameter. Children with a history of croup or recent upper respiratory tract infection (URTI) are particularly susceptible because residual airway inflammation and hyperreactivity may persist for weeks [1]. Although intraoperative airway management may be uncomplicated, delayed postoperative airway compromise can occur. This case illustrates rapid progression from mild stridor to severe airway obstruction and respiratory failure following routine hypospadias surgery.

Case Report:

A 22-month-old male child (ASA I) with a history of croup and stridor three months before surgery presented

for second-stage hypospadias repair. His preoperative examination was unremarkable except for the prior airway history. He received oral midazolam for premedication. General anesthesia with a caudal block was administered without difficulty, and a non-cuffed endotracheal tube passed easily. Dexamethasone 0.6 mg/kg was given intravenously at the conclusion of surgery.

In the recovery unit, the child-maintained oxygen saturation at 92% but developed inspiratory stridor and upper airway obstruction. Nebulized epinephrine (0.5 mL of 1:4000 diluted in 3 mL saline) and IV hydrocortisone (75 mg) were administered [2,3,4]. His stridor improved within minutes (Wesley croup score [5] decreased to 3).

Three hours later, he developed recurrent stridor and oxygen desaturation (80–82%) during crying, with a worsening Wesley score (7). He was transferred to the pediatric intensive care unit (PICU) for high-flow nasal

cannula (HFNC) support. Oxygenation improved to 94%. Chest X-ray revealed bilateral opacities consistent with atelectasis or aspiration. Venous blood gas showed hypoxemia and lactate of 2.9 mmol/L.

Despite repeated doses of nebulized epinephrine, budesonide, and IV dexamethasone, respiratory distress worsened (Wesley score 12), prompting intubation. C-MAC laryngoscopy showed no supraglottic edema, but advancing a non-cuffed 4.5 mm tube encountered resistance just below the vocal cords suggestive of

subglottic edema [6,7]. A large amount of greenish secretion was suctioned. A central venous line was inserted, and empiric antibiotics were initiated. MRSA screening returned positive.

Follow-up imaging showed improving lower-lobe opacities with newly developing faint infiltrates in the upper zones. The child demonstrated steady clinical improvement and was extubated after 72 hours. He was discharged on oral antibiotics with outpatient follow-up.

Figure 1: Clinical image related to case report

Figure 2: Clinical image related to case report

Figure 3: Clinical image related to case report

MRSA Screen - Accession: 000632026006000874
Result Status - Auth (Verified)

DISCUSSION:

Postoperative stridor typically results from **laryngospasm, airway edema, or dynamic airway collapse**. Children with a history of croup remain at increased risk for airway reactivity even months after the initial illness. In this patient, although anesthesia and extubation were uneventful, delayed airway edema occurred postoperatively [8].

Agitation and crying likely increased negative intrathoracic pressure, aggravating dynamic airway collapse and edema. Early treatment with systemic corticosteroids and nebulized epinephrine is well-established for **post-extubation croup and stridor**. However, progressive symptoms despite medical therapy require PICU transfer and airway stabilization [8,9].

Pulmonary involvement manifesting as atelectasis or aspiration-related pneumonitis may occur secondary to airway obstruction, ineffective secretion clearance, or aspiration of oral/gastric contents. Greenish secretions at intubation support this possibility [10,11]. Mechanical ventilation ensured airway protection and allowed airway and lung recovery.

The need for **high-flow nasal cannula support followed by endotracheal intubation and mechanical ventilation** reflects the severity of airway compromise and lung involvement. Importantly, timely airway stabilization in a controlled intensive care setting likely prevented further deterioration. The subsequent gradual improvement and successful extubation after resolution of airway edema and pulmonary pathology support the diagnosis of a **reversible, inflammation-driven process** rather than structural airway abnormality [12,13].

This case demonstrates that preoperative airway history is critical in children undergoing elective procedures. Even remote episodes of croup warrant caution, extended monitoring, and preparedness for escalation.

CONCLUSION:

Postoperative stridor in pediatric patients can progress rapidly to airway obstruction and respiratory failure. Children with a history of croup require heightened perioperative vigilance. Early recognition, prompt treatment, careful radiologic interpretation, and timely escalation to PICU care are essential for preventing severe complications. Thorough preoperative assessment and postoperative monitoring remain key to safe pediatric anesthetic practice.

Patient Consent:

Written informed consent for publication of this case report was obtained from the child's legal guardian.

Conflicts of Interest:

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Funding:

No funding was received for this work.

Acknowledgments:

We acknowledge the PICU and pediatric surgery teams for their dedication to patient care.

REFERENCES:

1. Coté CJ, Lerman J, Anderson BJ. **A Practice of Anesthesia for Infants and Children.** 6th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2019. p. 721–726.
2. Coté CJ, Lerman J, Anderson BJ. **A Practice of Anesthesia for Infants and Children.** 6th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2019. p. 730–735.
3. Davis PJ, Cladis FP, Motoyama EK, editors. **Smith’s Anesthesia for Infants and Children.** 9th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2017. p. 536–540.
4. Kliegman RM, St. Geme JW, Blum NJ, Shah SS, Tasker RC, Wilson KM, editors. **Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics.** 21st ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2020. p. 2085–2087.
5. Kliegman RM, St. Geme JW, Blum NJ, Shah SS, Tasker RC, Wilson KM, editors. **Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics.** 21st ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2020. p. 2078–2081.
6. Miller RD, Cohen NH, Eriksson LI, Fleisher LA, Wiener-Kronish JP, Young WL, editors. **Miller’s Anesthesia.** 9th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2020. p. 2758–2762.
7. Coté CJ, Lerman J, Anderson BJ. **A Practice of Anesthesia for Infants and Children.** 6th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2019. p. 724–729.
8. Coté CJ, Lerman J, Anderson BJ. **A Practice of Anesthesia for Infants and Children.** 6th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2019. p. 724–735.
9. Tait AR, Malviya S. Anesthesia for the child with an upper respiratory tract infection. **Anesthesiology.** 2005;102(2):314–326.
10. Kliegman RM, St. Geme JW, Blum NJ, Shah SS, Tasker RC, Wilson KM, editors. **Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics.** 21st ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2020. p. 2152–2156.
11. Miller RD, Cohen NH, Eriksson LI, Fleisher LA, Wiener-Kronish JP, Young WL, editors. **Miller’s Anesthesia.** 9th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2020. p. 2762–2766.
12. Fuhrman BP, Zimmerman JJ, editors. **Pediatric Critical Care.** 5th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2017. p. 911–918.
13. Coté CJ, Lerman J, Anderson BJ. **A Practice of Anesthesia for Infants and Children.** 6th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2019. p. 735–742, 748–750.